

Analysis Of Policy Development Models For Strengthening Character Education Based On Islamic Education Values In The First Middle Education Unit In Karawang District

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received October 29, 2020</p> <p>Accepted December 24, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Policy, Education, Character, Islam</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4393076</p>	<p><i>Character education policies in Indonesia Photo in Presidential Regulation No. 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education which explains the main values of strengthening character education, namely religious, nationalist, independent, mutual cooperation and integrity. The issuance of a national policy as the basis for the implementation of education in Indonesia does not necessarily make its implementation run smoothly, this is due to the lack of understanding of the character education policy and its development model in various educational units and the lack of collaboration between stakeholders in implementing the character education policy. This research can also be used as a mainstay to support the main strengthening of other Character Education; one of them is the Principal and Teacher of PAI in the junior secondary education unit in Karawang Regency; which incidentally is the locus of this research. PIE; as subjects that should be connected with Character Education appear to be separate running entities. This research was conducted using a descriptive qualitative research method with a case study approach. The purpose of this study was to identify and analyze the development of character education policies implemented by educational units based on existing regulations. This research is expected to provide recommendations and research guarantees in the form of a compatible and relevant character education policy development model and is applied to junior secondary education units in Karawang Regency.</i></p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Murthy said that skills, creativity, and independence are three very important things that every student must have in order to be able to face the realities of his life, be creative in providing solutions to existing problems (Amirudin & Muzaki, 2019b: 280). Murthy's opinion is not entirely correct, because there is one most basic thing, namely character. The idea of character education has increasingly surfaced with the emergence of the Mental Revolution National Movement which is part of Pak Jokowi's Nawacita by placing character education at the primary and secondary education levels because it is an important element in shaping the character of students in the future by basing on four dimensions of character processing, namely heart exercise. (Ethics), Feelings (Aesthetic), Mindfulness (Literacy), Sports (Kinesthetic). The implementation of the character education policy still faces various problems, the implementation of the policy is not yet optimal due to the lack of understanding of the education unit in implementing character education policies in making character education policy development models based on the implementation of cultural bases and community bases with local wisdom values that are in accordance with the peculiarities of the each education unit, so that so far the implementation of character education policies in educational units has focused more on the application of class-based implementation models that emphasize class management. This is deemed ineffective because we believe that quality education can be achieved if the teaching process runs effectively, also runs smoothly and in accordance with the learning objectives (Amirudin & Muzaki, 2019a). Apart from that, another problem is that there is no collaboration between stakeholders in the implementation of character education policies. Even though in its implementation, this character education policy requires the involvement of various parties, not only education units, namely schools but also parents, community, government.

The central government and local governments must collaborate to revitalize and strengthen the education ecosystem to support the expansion of the implementation of character education. One of them is the role in meeting the quality standards for the implementation of character education policies in the preparation of Human Resources, Facilities and Infrastructure and Budget that support the implementation of the character education policy. This is also done by the Minister of Religion through the Regulation of the Minister of Religion Number 2 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Strengthening Character Education. The articles

in it contain synergistic steps to support the successful implementation of strengthening character education, especially within the Ministry of Religion. One of the important points in it is the role of Religious Education in an effort to strengthen the character of the community (Students). With this regulation, Religious Education in schools is not only limited to compulsory subjects; but it becomes the initial foundation for the realization of students with character. In addition, Islamic Religious Education in Islamic schools can play a role in efforts to foster all the intellectual potential (intellectual, spiritual and emotional) of its students (Budianto et al., 2020: 488) However, if we look at the level of implementation; it seems that this impression is not yet obvious in religious subjects. Religious Education (PAI) appears to be a different entity from character education; which should be linked. This then made researchers interested in examining more deeply by formulating the research title "Analysis of Policy Development Model of Strengthening Character Education Based on the Values of Islamic Religious Education in the Junior Secondary Education Unit in Karawang Regency. Based on the problem and the title. It is very important to research because this research is oriented towards developing development-based policies and fostering the character of the nation through character education policies which are currently one of the government's priority programs in the field of education. So that it is very important to carry out this research, with the hope that the results of this study are able to provide solutions to the research problems above in the form of thought contributions through recommendations for appropriate models in supporting government policies in nation development through character education. This research is proposed in a leading research scheme because this study aims to produce research outputs that are expected to be able to create new innovations in the form of conceptual recommendations related to character education policy development models that can be implemented in research partners. In addition, the research topics studied in this research are also one of the leading themes in the 2020-2024 Unsika research roadmap.

Literature Review

The state of the art in this research is taken from various scientific journals, both international journals and national journals. These studies are used as a frame of reference for the author in researching and studying problems related to character education. The following are several journals that also discuss research topics related to character education: An international journal entitled "Measuring Student Perception to personal characters building in education: an Indonesian case in implementing new curriculum in high school". This study discusses the implementation of the 2013 curriculum applied in Indonesia, where this research focuses on the preparation of instruments to measure and evaluate the character education application program through the 2013 curriculum and determine the impact of the program on students' personal character. This study developed 21 instrument items that represent 6 dimensions to measure the effect of character education on student academic achievement. The 6 dimensions are academic ability, religious values, honesty, creativity and innovation, religious tolerance, and discipline. The results show that based on the measurement results with 21 instrument items, there are 5 dimensions that show a positive influence on student academic achievement although not too significant, and 1 dimension shows a significant effect on student academic achievement, namely the dimension of tolerance (Fahmy, 2015).

Further research in an international journal entitled "Inculcating character education through EFL teaching in Indonesian state schools." This research discusses the application of character education through EFL teaching in public schools. The results of this study explain that the implementation of character education emphasizes the role of the teacher in transmitting the values of character education in learning activities. Where this is determined by the preference value of each teacher when in class by integrating character education values into the learning material that will be taught to students, this is done based on regulative discourse and instructional discourse (Qoyyimah, 2016).

Further research is an international journal entitled "Character Education For Golden Generation 2045 (National Character Building for Indonesian Golden Years)". This research discusses the development of national character through education in order to achieve Indonesia's Vision in 2045, namely to become a developed and strong country. The results showed that several values that should be used as indicators in the development of education in Indonesia are 1) Strengthening academic abilities and the value of honesty; 2) fostering nationalism; 3) cultivate tolerance and respect; 4) fostering democratic values; 5) enforcing the law (Rokhman, 2013).

Further research in the National Journal entitled "Strengthening Character Education in Madrasah". By Nur Khamalah (2017) discusses the implementation of strengthening character education in madrasas where there are several factors that are inhibiting factors for the implementation of strengthening education in madrasas, such as 1) Character values developed in madrasas have not been described in representative indicators; 2) Madrasas have not been able to choose character values that match their vision; 3) Teachers' understanding of character education is still not comprehensive; 4) Teachers have not been able to choose character values in accordance with the subject they are teaching; 5) Teachers do not have adequate competence to integrate character values in the subjects they are teaching; 6) Teachers have not been able to become role models for the character values they choose. The results of this study explain that strengthening character

education in madrasas must be adjusted to the function of character education itself, namely: 1) Forming and developing the potential of students to think well, have good hearts and behave in accordance with the Pancasila philosophy; 2) Sorting out the culture of the nation itself and filtering the culture of other nations that are not in accordance with the cultural values of the nation and the character of the nation with dignity (Khamalah, 2017).

Furthermore, the journal entitled "Analysis of the Implementation of Character Education Policies at the Taman Siswa College, Turen District, Malang Regency", this study discusses the analysis of the implementation of character education policies at Taman Siswa Elementary School, Turen which consists of 1) understanding and explaining the implementation of the Character Education Policy at Taman SD Elementary Student, Turen; 2) understanding the obstacles in implementing the character education in SD Taman Siswa, Turen; 3) knowing the school's strategy to overcome obstacles in the implementation of character education at SD Taman Siswa. The results of his research indicate that the implementation of the character education policy at SD Taman Siswa Turen runs well despite several obstacles. These obstacles are the lack of teacher professionalism, the negative impact of globalization on students, and the lack of the role of parents and society in implementing character education policies. And to overcome these obstacles, strategies that can be done are: 1) increasing professionalism and enthusiasm "among" teachers; 2) applying character education methods by "understanding, feeling, nglakoni"; 3) strengthening the role of parents and society by increasing the role of the school committee (Acetylena, 2013)

Furthermore, research in the National journal entitled Character Building through Islamic Religious Education. The study discusses the role of Islamic religious education in schools in shaping the character of students. Through PAI learning, students are taught *aqidah* as their religious basis, taught the Koran and hadith as their life guidelines, taught *fiqh* as legal signs in worship, teaches Islamic history as an example of life, and teaches morals as guidelines for human behavior whether in good or good categories. bad. The results showed that 1) the success of Islamic Education learning in schools was also determined by the application of appropriate learning methods. 2) professional teachers are needed in the sense that they are knowledgeable, have good character and are able to be role models for their students. 3) learning is not only carried out in the classroom but coupled with religious extracurricular activities which are carried out seriously as part of learning. 4) all teachers should be able to implement religious education in the whole material taught as a form of overall character education. (Ainiyah, 2013).

Based on the previous research above as a state of the art, it can be concluded that the six research journals have different research focuses with the research that the authors will study. Where these journals examine character education as a technical concept related to the program structure and curriculum structure applied in classroom learning activities by emphasizing the dominant role of schools in the application of character education. Whereas in this study, the researcher examines character education from a different point of view where the researcher discusses in depth related to policy analysis and also the development model of the policy by not only emphasizing the role of the school but the involvement of various stakeholders such as the community, local government, the world. businesses, academics and cultural activists in the implementation and development of these policies. So that the implementation is not only limited to class-based implementation but also culture-based and community-based implementation.

Research methods

The research method used in this research is descriptive research with a qualitative approach which aims to understand the phenomenon of character education policies and the development of policy models based on the values of Islamic religious education in junior secondary education units in Karawang district. According to Sudaryono (2017) qualitative research is research that seeks to analyze social life by describing the social world from the point of view or interpretation of individuals (informants) in a natural setting. Meanwhile, descriptive research according to Sudaryono (2017) means that descriptive research is intended to describe a state or phenomenon as it is. The qualitative research chosen is a type of case study. A case study is a research strategy in which researchers carefully investigate a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals by focusing on a case intensively and in detail (Cresswell, 2016).

Data collection was carried out in two ways, namely literature study and field studies. 1) Literature study is obtained from data from international and national journals, books, laws and regulations, government documents as well as booklets and guidebooks from the ministry regarding character education issues. 2) Field studies using observation and interview techniques, where researchers observe and participate directly and interview informants who have been determined in the study. Primary data sources in this study, researchers used guidelines and recorded interviews with main informants and supporting informants regarding character education policies based on Islamic religious values in the junior secondary education unit, Karawang district. The main informants in this study were the Head of the Ministry of Religion of Karawang Regency, the Head of the PAIS Section of the Ministry of Religion of the Karawang Regency, the Principal of Schools and School Committees, PAI teachers in junior secondary education units and the Regional Government. Secondary data

sources in this study were obtained using literature studies conducted on many books and data obtained from the research site.

According to Miles and Huberman in Sugiyono (2017) data analysis is divided into three parts, namely Data Reduction, Data Display, and Conclusion or Verification (Conclusion drawing / verifying) The steps in data reduction in this study are (1) strengthening and sharpening the analysis starting from the results of interviews with informants from the ministry of religion (the Head of the Ministry of Religion and Kasi PAIS), local governments and from the school (principals, PAI teachers, School Committee); (2) classifying and adjusting the results of interviews with related data obtained from observations and documentation related to the implementation of strengthening character education, national documents such as guidebooks for strengthening character education, booklets and others; (3) reviewing the relevance of research results and discussion with problem formulations; (4) sorting back the relevant data with the research title, and (5) combining the data so that conclusions can be drawn and verified as the final result of the discussion. Data Display in qualitative research can be done in the form of short narratives, charts, relationships between categories, flowcharts, and so on. Conclusion / Verification (Conclusion Drawing / Verification) The conclusions in this study are new findings found from the research results in the form of recommendations related to policy development models for strengthening character education.

Research Results and Discussion

This research was conducted by involving a number of junior secondary education units as well as Islamic education teachers in Karawang district. These schools are SMPN 6 Karawang Barat, SMPN 1 Rengasdengklok, SMPN 1 Karawang Barat, SMPN 1 Pakisjaya, SMPN 3 Telagasari, SMPN 5 Karawang Barat, SMPN 1 Batujaya, SMPN 3 Klari, SMPIT Al-Irsyad Al-Islamiyyah Karawang, SMPN 2 Kotabaru, SMPN 2 Tirtamulya, SMPN 1 East Telukjambe, SMPN 6 West Karawang, SMPN 1 Cikampek, SMPN 3 Karawang Barat, SMPN 2 Tirtajaya, Islamic Junior High School Al-Mudriky, SMPN 1 Tirtajaya, SMPIT Mentari Ilmu, SMP Pupuk Kujang, and SMPN 2 Majalaya.

Strengthening Character Education (PPK) must be implemented in educational institutions. This refers to Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017. Then it was strengthened by Regulation of the Minister of Religion Number 2 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Strengthening Character Education. Meanwhile, in the context of implementation in Karawang Regency, especially in the Junior High School Education unit, it can be seen from the results of the study that 71.4% of schools implemented character education strengthening programs effectively and 28.6% of schools implemented ineffective character education. In the context of Islamic education teachers implementing PPK in classroom learning activities as many as 81% of Islamic Education teachers implemented PPK in class effectively, while 19% were less effective. Among the driving factors for the effective implementation of PPK in various schools is the support of regulations from the Principal that encourages the effectiveness of this activity, besides that the collaboration of all academicians of school institutions is also a determining factor for the success of this program, because this program is designed for synergy and correlation of all school elements. Then adequate school facilities are also a determinant of the effectiveness of this activity because it cannot be denied that policy implementation will be successful if it has a strong carrying capacity, one of which is facilities and infrastructure. Another factor that is then important is modeling. Modeling is a crucial factor driving the effectiveness of this program. If the program is not balanced with exemplary, it is best if the results will not be as expected. Likewise with the support of the school committee. The school committee must support all school policies, the committee has an important role in the sustainability of this policy.

Meanwhile, the factors inhibiting the effectiveness of this policy, among others, are other subject teachers who neglect this policy. So that policies that should run synergistically become a little lame. Inadequate parental supervision is also an inhibiting factor. There is still an opinion that parents interpret learning only at school. Students' understanding regarding reading the Koran is also an inhibiting factor for this effectiveness so that concentration on cultivating character is not as easy as for people who can read the Al-Qur'an. Communication is also one of the inhibiting factors, many things must be communicated between schools and parents. This is an important note because parents are the main partners in the implementation of this policy. The level of student awareness varies so that it is difficult to implement PPK consistently and comprehensively; so that there are some students who do not understand the importance of discipline in carrying out activities.

PPK through integrated religious education is carried out through class-based, school-based, and / or community-based implementation. Class-based implementation is done by: a. integrating the learning process with the implementation of religious values; b. compiling a lesson plan with due regard to the implementation of religious values; c. strengthening classroom management, selecting learning methods, and assessments based on the implementation of religious values; and D. develop local content nuanced implementation of religious values. In relation to these activities, as many as 52.4% of PAI teachers only did part of the activities while 47.6% carried out all activities.

PPK activities are carried out with a variety of activities including intracurricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities. Based on the research results, 61.9% of schools applied PPK in all activities while 28.6% applied PPK in only two activities, and 9.5% applied PPK only in intracurricular activities. Among the implementation of PPK activities in intracurricular form are as follows: initial habituation of the Teaching and Learning Process by reading the Koran, Asmaul Husna, ending learning activities by praying, always collaborating in group activities, always checking the cleanliness of the class, before learning muhadoroh activities student lectures and learning tahsin Al-Qur'an. Meanwhile, the implementation of PPK in co-curricular activities is carried out in Flag Ceremony activities, holding an honesty canteen, habituating infaq and alms, carrying out PHBI activities, welcoming students at the school gate with musafahah, habituation of dhuha prayers and dzuhur prayers in congregation and outing classes per semester. For extracurricular activities, the implementation of PPK is carried out in the form of BTQ, ROHIS, calligraphy, kasidah, marawis, worship practices, scouts and PMR.

Meanwhile, in relation to PAI values which are integrated with PPK 60% of PAI teachers say all values (Religious, Nationalist, Independent, Integrity, and Mutual Cooperation) are integrated with PPK, while 35% of PAI teachers say that only religious values are integrated with PPK, the rest 5% said that mutual cooperation was integrated with PPK.

Conclusions and suggestions

Character Education Strengthening Activities are carried out well in the junior secondary education unit in the Karawang district. The data shows that the majority of junior high schools in Karawang district carry out PPK activities effectively. This is because there is still solid cooperation between parties, in this case the school principal, Islamic Education teachers, committees and policy makers. Problems in character education and student needs for character education are the basis for formulating character education policy formulas. The estimation and selection of policies were carried out on a limited basis with the involvement of teachers and school principals. Policy recommendations proposed through closed meetings and discussions are policies that have relevance to efforts to educate students according to the values that characterize schools.

The program and implementation of character education are adjusted to the school's abilities and the distinctive characteristics inherent in the school. Programs and implementation of character education for schools are carried out in intracurricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities. The main obstacle faced by schools in character education is the weakness of the quality assurance system for character education, the weak support of the information system to support quality character education activities. The budget is limited and the quality culture has not yet functioned as a differentiator for schools that focus on character education from schools that do not have character education orientation. The quality assurance system in implementing character education is still informal. Schools do not have a quality assurance system in character education. This condition causes the process of implementing character education programs to be more routine in nature without any evaluation and control through the system. Implementation of character education in schools requires policies and support for a quality assurance system that can provide assurance that each program, education implementation is carried out with quality standards in accordance with the vision and mission of the school.

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